

ON-Harmony: A multi-site, multi-modal travelling-heads resource for brain MRI harmonisation with integration of UK Biobank scanners

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Introduction: MRI quantifiability is hindered by non-biological sources of variability, e.g scanner hardware/software¹⁻³. Several approaches aim to standardise/harmonise acquisition and processing⁴⁻⁶, but lack of harmonisation is an open challenge. We ran one of the most comprehensive, freely accessible, multi-modal travelling heads studies, ON-Harmony⁷⁻⁹ (Fig1): 20 subjects, each scanned in up to 8 3T scanners, 3 vendors (Siemens/Philips/GE) and 5 modalities (T1w/T2w/dMRI/swMRI/fMRI), plus within-scanner/within-subject repeats, enabling within-scanner, between-scanner and between-subject variability to be mapped across multi-modal imaging-derived phenotypes (IDPs). We have recently scanned 11 of the subjects at the Stockport UK Biobank (UKB) imaging centre (Reading UKB centre also planned), enabling linkage of UKB population-level imaging data with various clinical scanners. Here, we showcase the data and reuse scenarios for assessing harmonisation efficacy.

Methods: ON-Harmony consists of 2 primary phases (10 subjects each), plus the UKB extension.

Acquisition protocols were aligned with the UKB imaging study¹⁰, while respecting best practices and hardware limitations (i.e. parameters not simply nominally-matched)⁸. Each subject was scanned in at least 6 different scanners (out of a collection of 8 scanners) and 9 subjects had 5 additional within-scanner repeats. 11 participants were re-scanned at the UKB centre (1 subject with 5 within-scanner repeats). All data underwent quality control through visual inspection and then using MRIQC¹¹ (T1w/T2w/fMRI) and eddyQC¹² (dMRI). Data were processed with a modified version⁸ of the UKB pipeline¹³. Hundreds of IDPs were derived for each session, allowing us to quantify IDP variability.

Results: Fig2a shows a subject's raw data, depicting sessions across scanners (columns) and modalities (rows). We assessed between-session IDP similarity for within-scanner, between-scanner, between-subject pools (Fig2b). Between-subject variability has little overlap with scan-rescan variability, however, it overlaps quite substantially with between-scanner variability. We explored how ON-Harmony can be used to assess harmonisation efficacy, e.g. ComBat^{14,15} (explicit harmonisation). Pre/post harmonisation between-scanner variability was compared to within-scanner variability (Fig3) for dMRI tract-wise FA measures. Reductions in between-scanner variability following harmonisation were revealed but did not match the within-scanner baseline. ON-Harmony can also be used to assess pipeline/tool generalisability across scanners (implicit harmonisation). Fig4 shows generalisability of tractography for FSL-XTRACT¹⁶. For each scanner, subject-averaged tract maps were obtained and correlated against a UKB atlas, with moderate-high correlation values across all scanners and generally consistent trends across vendors/phases, although with some exceptions (GE-A was a low gradient system with a single-shell protocol). Such comparisons showcase how ON-Harmony can be used to assess susceptibility of tools/pipelines to between-scanner effects.

Conclusion: We have presented a comprehensive harmonisation resource (ON-Harmony) for multimodal neuroimaging data, based on a travelling-heads paradigm. ON-Harmony is openly released, freely available⁹ and can be used to assess harmonisation efficacy and to develop new vendor agnostic tools/pipelines. The novel UK Biobank extension will enable direct linkage of a representative sets of scanners from all vendors with one of the largest population-level studies.

References: [1] Pinto et al. *Front. Neurosci.* 14 (2020). [2] Han et al. *NeuroImage* 32:180 (2006). [3] Friedman et al. *Hum. Brain Mapp.* 29:958 (2008). [4] Potvin et al. *NeuroImage Clin.* 24:101943 (2019). [5] Chen et al. *NeuroImage Clin.* 24:101943 (2019). [6] Layton et al. *Magn. Reson. Med.* 77:1544 (2017). [7] Warrington et al. *Sci. Data* 12:609 (2025). [8] Warrington et al. *Imaging Neurosci.* (2023). [9] ON-Harmony, <https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds004712/versions/2.0.1>. [10] Miller et al. *Nat. Neurosci.* 19:1523 (2016). [11] Esteban et al. *PLOS ONE* 12:e0184661 (2017). [12] Bastiani et al. *NeuroImage* 184:801 (2019). [13] Alfaro-Almagro et al. *NeuroImage* 166:400 (2018). [14] Fortin et al. *NeuroImage* 167:104 (2018). [15] Fortin et al. *NeuroImage* 161:149 (2017). [16] Warrington et al. *NeuroImage* 217: 116923 (2020).

Figure 1: ON-Harmony: a multi-modal travelling-heads harmonisation resource

Figure 2: a) Example of a single subject's data. b) Between-session similarity for different pools of variability

Figure 3: Example of assessing explicit harmonisation efficacy

Figure 4: a) Tractography results for ON-Harmony phases and the UKB reference. b) Tract-wise correlations across vendors/phases